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Research Article

**A STUDY TO COMPARE SYMPTOMS OF ABDOMINAL
HYSTERECTOMY AS IDENTIFIED CLINICALLY WITH
THOSE PROVED HISTOPATHOLOGICALLY**¹Dr. Usama Khalid, ²Dr. Tayyaba Anwar, ³Dr. Adil Majeed¹Medical Officer, RHC 148/EB District Vehari²Woman Medical Officer, BHU 455/EB District Vehari³Medical Officer, BHU Verum Chak 4, Chunian, Kasur**Abstract:**

Objective: Carried out the present study to find out the relationship among medical symptom and ultimate histopathological analysis of hysterectomy sample. **Study Design:** Cross-Sectional Descriptive Study. **Place and Duration:** Held the present research study from March, 2016 to February, 2018 in the department of gynaecology at Services hospital Lahore. **Methodology:** Selected all those patients for the current research who were suffering from gynaecological infections and taking the treatment of hysterectomy. Excluded all those patients who were having vaginal hysterectomy and obstetric hysterectomy. Collected the data information about medical statistics, symptoms of hysterectomy and demographic features and made a record of all information on a proforma which was predesigned for this purpose. Took surgical samples for test of histopathology and examined the resultant reports and made the comparison of surgery indications with it. **Results:** Carried out major gynaecological surgeries total 313 in number from which abdominal hysterectomies were 53.9 %. Average age of the patients was 44.2±5.2 and multiparous females were more in strength. Most common indication showed were mass in lower abdomen as 8.3%, anomalous uterine bleeding as 59.8% and abnormal uterine bleeding with pain as 21.9%. Frequent posing sign of hysterectomy was adenomyosis (8.9%) and dysfunctional uterine bleeding (39.6%), followed by fibroid (29.6%). Preoperative analysis confirmed 100 % in cases of pelvic inflammatory disease, adnexal masses, endometriosis, malignancy and endometrial hyperplasia according to the final histopathological result reports of hysterectomy specimens. Found inequality among histopathological and clinical analysis in cases of adenomyosis in 23.7 % histopathological and 8.9 % clinical, fibroid in 32.6 % histopathological and 29.6 % clinical and dysfunctional uterine bleeding in 16.6 % histopathological and 39.6 % clinical. **Conclusion:** The pre-operative diagnosis for hysterectomy in cases of fibroid, malignancy, endometriosis, endometrial hyperplasia and pelvic inflammatory disease symptoms are well correlating with histopathological reports. Particularly for the management of malignant disease and for confirmation of diagnosis histopathology is very necessary.

Keywords: histopathology, adenomyosis, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, Abdominal hysterectomy.

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INTRODUCTION:

Operation which generally carried out in the whole world for Gynaecological surgery is hysterectomy [01]. In United Kingdom and England Approximately 01 lakh in a year and > 70 thousand per year cases of hysterectomy were there respectively [02]. Researches on prevalence of hysterectomy are not available in Pakistan [03]. Prevalence of hysterectomy in female population of the world in the age of 64 years is 40.01% [04]. Including uterus and adnexa hysterectomy operation provides exclusive curing in numerous diseases such as malignancy, pelvic organ prolapses, pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), endometriosis, adenomyosis, dysfunctional uterine bleeding (DUB) and fibroids [05].

Procedures adapted for hysterectomy operation might include vaginal or laparoscopic and abdominal. Through abdominal route, abdominal hysterectomy includes whole elimination of cervix and uterus. Corresponding to the method adapted for operation there are different types of abdominal hysterectomy such as extra facial hysterectomy, interfacial hysterectomy, radical hysterectomy, subtotal and total hysterectomy [06]. Although the most common route for hysterectomy is laparotomy but currently there is just no consensus on the specific techniques or best route for operation [07]. Due to equivalent or expressively improved results on bases of all parameters, vaginal hysterectomy might be performed in predilection to abdominal hysterectomy each time when it is workable as concluded in a Cochrane appraisal about surgical method to hysterectomy for caring gynaecological disease [08]. Total laparoscopic hysterectomy is a harmless substitute to open surgery for endometrial cancer as well as for benign indicators as indicated in some prospective controlled researches [09, 10]. According to the findings of a study the death rate calculated is from 0.50 to 02 per thousand cases [02]. Where adjuvant treatment is reliant on upon grade and invasion level of disease, diagnostic value of histopathological examination is well described in patients with malignancy. Found ½ to 2 out of one thousand as death rate due to hysterectomy [02].

Patients with malignancy are source of good explanation for diagnostic value of histopathological examination because adjuvant treatment of such patients is depending upon extent of invasion disease and its grade. Histopathology establishes the diagnosis of adenomyosis whereas diagnosis of exclusion carried out through DUB. Each hysterectomy case must be referred to histopathological examination as the best diagnosis is only through histology. The main purpose of this

research is to compare symptoms of abdominal hysterectomy as identified clinically with those proved histopathologically and discover prevailing differences.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

Organized the current cross-sectional research study in the department of gynaecology at mayo hospital Lahore from March, 2016 to February, 2018. Excluded every obstetric and vaginal hysterectomies. During study period carried out a total number of 313 major gynaecological operations. Estimated sample size was 168 as calculated by using WHO calculator of sample sizing [11], supposing the proportion 58.8% [06] patients of abdominal hysterectomies with 95.0 % confidence level and margin of error as 7.46 %. Incorporated 169 abdominal hysterectomies in the current study. Selected every patient from OPD (out-patient department). Through the help of medical staff, before performing the surgery corrected the anaemia and other medical issues. Including clinical features and demographic characteristics recorded all information by using predesigned proforma. Documented and counted as the sign for the process was only one dominant finding. Discharged the patients after 04 days to 06 days from operation and carried out follow up on the intervals of 14 days. Used 10 % formalin to save the hysterectomy samples and further sent them to pathology department.

Entered the collected information in SPSS software V.20 for analysis. For consonance among histopathological diagnosis and clinical signs, calculated the ratio in percentage and occurrence, applied Kappa test to understand agreement among histopathological clinical and conclusions. Calculated mean standard deviation for equality and age. Considered the Kappa value of >0.70 as well significant.

RESULTS:

Carried out 313 main gynecological operation during 2 years period of current study, out of which 53.9 % (169) cases were of abdominal hysterectomies. Common clinical characteristics of the cases described in table number 01 below. Considered 44.30±5.30 years of age as mean age. Multiparous female patients were 59.20 % as described above. Very general problems complained by patients were as chronic pelvic pain in 06 %, post-menopausal bleeding shown by 6.50 %, mass in lower abdomen by 8.30 %, chronic pelvic pain and heavy menstrual loss complained by 21.90 % and heavy menstrual loss only by 59.80 % of patients.

Table No 01: Parity Clinical Report in Abdominal Hysterectomy Cases {Mean Age = 44.3(SD±5.30) years}

Parity	Frequency	Percentage (%)
P5 & above	100	59.20
Nullipara	05	03.00
P1-4	64	37.90

Table No 02: Clinical Report in Abdominal Hysterectomy Cases {Mean Age = 44.3(SD±5.30) years}

Symptoms	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Postmenopausal bleeding	11	6.50
Mass in lower abdomen	14	8.30
Pain in heavy menstrual loss	37	21.9
Pain in lower abdomen	06	3.60
Heavy menstrual loss	101	59.8

Enumerated several signs for hysterectomy in table number 03 below. Carried out hysterectomies mainly as for 03 % malignancy, 6.50 % for polyp, 4.10 % for adnexal masses, 8.90 % for adenomyosis, 29.60 % for fibroid and 39.60 % for dysfunctional uterine bleeding.

Table No 03: Clinical Symptoms for Abdominal Hysterectomy

Symptoms	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Pelvic inflammatory disease	03	1.80
Endometrial hyperplasia	06	3.60
Endometriosis	05	3.00
Malignancy	05	3.00
Polyp	11	6.50
Adenexal masses	07	4.10
Adenomyosis	15	8.90
Fibroid uterus	50	29.6
Dysfunctional uterine bleeding	67	39.6

Differentiation among clinical diagnosis and histological diagnosis described below in table number 04. Amounting to 2.40 % clinical under diagnosis, verified leiomyoma through histopathology in 32.0 % cases vs 29.60 % as clinical diagnosis. Diagnose adenomyosis clinically in 8.90 % whereas, 23.70 % cases confirmed through histopathology. Hence, 14.80 % was there as clinical underestimation. However, in only 16.60 % cases dysfunctional uterine bleeding confirmed through histologically process and overestimated clinically in 39.60 %. According to findings of histopathology there was five cases of suspected malignancy as one case of mucinous carcinoma of ovary, three cases of endometrial cancer and one case of carcinoma of ovary.

Table No 04: Clinical Diagnosis vs Histopathological (169 Abdominal Hysterectomy Cases)

Symptoms	Histopathological Diagnosis (%)	Clinical Diagnosis (%)
Pelvic inflammatory disease	1.8	1.8
Endometrial hyperplasia	3.6	3.6
Endometriosis	3.0	3.0
Malignancy	3.0	3.0
Polyp	12.4	6.5
Adenaxal masses	4.1	4.1
Adenomyosis	23.7	8.9
Fibroid	32.0	29.6
Dysfunctional uterine bleeding	16.6	39.6

DISCUSSION:

During the period of postmenopausal and peri common surgical process carried out on female is hysterectomy. Carried out 313 main gynecological operation during 24 months period of current study, out of which abdominal hysterectomies cases were 53.9 % (169). Considered 44.30 ± 5.30 years of age as mean age and multiparous female cases were 59.20 % as mentioned before. With or without pelvic pain, heavy menstrual loss was the most common showed signs and with these signs high parity and perimenopausal age group are well known as associated. In some studies, by Bashir *et al*; Shergill SK *et al*; and Shakira P *et al*; showed 38.0%, 66.0 % and 42.50 % resultant symptoms respectively [3, 12, 13]. According to the findings and observations of present study the most commonly found symptom for hysterectomy was abnormal uterine bleeding which was there in 39.60 % patients whereas, only 16.59 % patients of abnormal uterine bleeding confirmed through histologically. Now this clearly displays a clinical over-diagnosis of abnormal uterine bleeding. The most common symptom for hysterectomy as described by many studies is abnormal uterine bleeding [03, 14]. Fibroids in 29.60 % cases considered as the 2nd most common symptom for hysterectomy. And fibroids indication for hysterectomy according to many other studies is the leading symptom [02, 04, 05]. Representing a minor clinical underestimation, leiomyoma was most frequent pathology on histopathology in 32.01 % cases. According to findings of many other studies it is the main pathology. Observations show the occurrence rate as 8.0 %, 48.0 %, 78.0 %, and 25.80 % in Sweden, Nigeria, USA and Abbah (city of Saudi

Arabia) respectively [06, 15, 16, 17]

Hence, on the frequency of uterine leiomyoma, cultural and geographical effects are very clear. Adenomyosis is known as second most common cause of hysterectomy. Carried out histological diagnosis of adenomyosis in 23.70 % hysterectomies whereas, carried out clinical diagnosis only in 8.90 % cases which show significant clinical underestimation. Frequency rate of adenomyosis in accordance to the studies from West Indies, Italy, Karachi, India and Lahore was as 06.0%, 24.90%, 24.0%, 26.0% and 27.20% respectively [05, 12, 13, 18, 19].

According to the findings of present study histopathologically confirmed polyp in 12.40 % cases and that is also same alike to the researches from Saudi Arabia and Pakistan as 13.40% and 10.0% respectively [20, 21]. In cases of adenexal masses and malignancy found inequality inside histological and clinical diagnosis. Found malignancy in 3.0% clinically and histologically confirmed in 3.0%. Got help for precise diagnosis from pre-operative biopsy and CT scan.

CONCLUSION:

With the clinical diagnosis as pelvic inflammatory disease, endometriosis, adenexal masses, endometrial hyperplasia, malignancy and fibroid found correlation of pathological and clinical procedures as very high. But with pre-operative clinical diagnosis of adenomyosis and dysfunctional uterine bleeding found poor co-relation. Particularly in the case of malignant disease for ensuring optimal management and confirmation of diagnosis, histopathology is very

necessary.

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